

The Coupling Constants Series and Photon Emission – 8T

O Manor

June 17, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constants series and in particular the insight regarding bosonic fields to be net curvature on the Lorentz manifold invoked stationary by Euler Lagrange operator, it is possible to re- describe the process of photon emission and interaction between two electrons. The paper is using the additional insight regarding the nature of bosons as closed strings, as proven by the 8T, since they are forming a cyclic group due to being generated by the same element.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

$$(e) = (3) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(5)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.14)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(\gamma)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.15)$$

Equations (1) to (1.13) describe the process of emission to the invariant three, proven the electron, assumed the electron for each higher term in the coupling series. equations (1.14) - (1.15) describe the invariant three as the generator of a cyclic group, meaning all bosonic propagations are sub elements of that group and so we prove they are closed cycles themselves. And so we can draw the interaction between two electrons and a photon emission in the following way:

As was proven, they cannot move at the same orientation of the distortion due to their prime number feature, combined together there will be a vanishing and so the coupling series than would not make sense. The end conclusion would than imply that the boson propagated from nowhere which is impossible.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)